

SOCIO-TECHNICAL PROCESS MODELLING REPORT (T3.3.): IOT PILOT SETUP IN VITICULTURE AND BEEKEEPING

LIVING LAB SMART VILLAGES NETWORK

SLOVENIA

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1. Summary

1.1. Name of living lab

Smart Villages Network (Mreža pametnih vasi)

1.2. Brief summary of living lab

Briefly describe the living lab to provide context [300 words]

The Smart Villages Network connects farmers, researchers, technology solution providers, and government representatives. Over the years we have cooperated and engaged in various projects and initiatives that complement and enrich each other, always with a clear focus on cultivating a smarter and more sustainable future for rural communities. Together, we co-create sustainable solutions, leveraging the benefits of technological advancements. Our primary focus involves harnessing IoT technology in wine and honey production through co-creation, prototyping, testing, and scaling up innovations.

1.3. Living lab participants

Briefly summarise the profile of the different actors involved in the living lab, and that were involved in the data collection activities (interviews, workshops, focus groups, etc.). [300 words]

In the data collection process, we have included different types of participants such as: farmers, researchers, business advisors, technology advisors and government representatives.

1.4. Timing of Data Collection activities

Please detail how was the Process Modelling data collection activity carried out, by reporting:

- General process followed (Example: we started reviewing reports of previous activities to check already collected data, then we took interviews to key informants, finally we organized a focus group)
 - A table or list with more details about the activities carried out and profiles of participants. Please, indicate all the previous project activities that contributed to providing data relevant to process modelling, as in the example table below:

Date / Type	Activity	Duration	Participants and background	Output
07/03/2023 (physical)	Living lab meeting	2h	5 participants (2 farmers, 2 researchers, 1 business advisor)	Focal action Situation. Gathering information, and needs from farmers, drafting 2 pilot cases (bees, wine).

30/03/2023 (physical)	On-farm visit for LL set up	2h	6 participants (background: 2 farmer + 1 data scientists, 2 researchers, 1 business advisor)	Analysis, of the current process and possible digital solution development; FAS development, collecting data
19/05/2023 (physical)	LL set up	1 day	10 participants (background: 2 farmer + 2 data scientists + 2 researchers, 1 PR, 3 representatives of the technology providers)	Sensor infrastructure instalation
16/06/2023 (physical)	LL set up	1 day	8 participants (background: 2 farmer + 1 data scientists + 2 researchers, 3 representatives of the technology providers)	Sensor infrastructure instalation
15/11/2023 (physical)	Workshop (WP3)	1.5 hours	12 participants (background: 3 farmers who use digital solutions + 2 farmers who don't use digital technology + 1 researcher (EU policies and innovative ecosystems) + 1 research (technology developer) + 1 business advisor + 2 technology advisors (IoT) + 1 technology advisor (data analysis) + 1 representative from the Ministry of digitalisation	Identify resources, capabilities, collaborations and innovations present and needed to solve the LL FAS problem statement; Analyze the digital ecosystem conduciveness by using the Socio-ecological framework to explore how it supports/hinders the resources, capabilities, collaborations and innovations necessary to address the LL FAS problem statement.
15/11/2023 (physical)	Focus group (WP4)	1.5 hours	8 participants (background: 2 farmers who use digital solutions + 1 farmer who don't use digital technology + 1 researcher (EU policies and innovative ecosystems) + 1 research (technology developer) + 1 business advisor + 1 technology advisors (IoT) + 1 representative from the government on policy	Exploring participant's views on the social, environmental, and economic costs and benefits associated with digitalization in agriculture.
12/04/2024 (physical)	Social -Human centred C&B analysis (WP4)	1h	3 participants (farmer, 2 researchers)	Interview on social costs and benefits with the beekeeper.

25/04/2024 (virtual)	Social -Human centred C&B analysis (WP4)	1h	5 participants (2 farmers, 2 researchers, 1 developer).	Interview on social costs and benefits with the wine producers.
10/05/2024 (physical)	Virtual Demo Event (WP5)	1 day	50+ participants (farmers, agricultural advisors, researchers, technology providers, students)	Showcasing the digital technologies applied to the LL demo farm.
Oktober 2024 (phone interview)	Additional data collection from the winemaker	1h	1 farmer	Detailed descriptions of on-farm activities

1.5. Summary of collected data

Please provide a narrative summary [half a page] of the data collection activities that have been carried out. Please also summarise the main outcomes that will be detailed in the rest of the document.

The first meeting with the two representatives of Demo Farms took place on 7.03.2023 in Maribor at business advisor’s location. The goal of the visit was analysis of the farmers current needs, processes on farms and possible digital solution implementation. Together we drafted a possible Focal Action Situation for Vineyard scenario and one for Honey production scenario and defined steps for future collaboration. We scheduled the next meeting on the demo farm (Doppler Winery) together with data scientist, mobile app developer and technical expert from University of Ljubljana.

Both FAS included installation of IoT infrastructure (and data collection) in order to optimise the farmers decision making and activities. This will positively influence better economic, environmental and social situation on the farms.

The farmer (Doppler Winery) provided an explanation of the current process of the activities carried out and the problems they face:

1. Connectivity issues due to the rugged terrain might be a problem for connecting any digital solution
2. The climate is significantly different in different parts of the vineyard, requiring different responses. Therefore “standard” IoT weather stations that are placed on one location on farm are not suitable for typical Slovenian hilly terrain. We should consider a “network” of sensors that are placed on different heights, sides of hills etc. but at the same time they need to communicate with the network.
3. The farm is in the process of converting to organic farming. Organic sprays must be applied to the vines as soon as a certain amount of rain falls. Information on the amount of rain at a micro-location is very important.
4. They are seeing significant climate change, which requires them to think about how to adapt to it. They need more knowledge, information and data.

Researchers at UL helped with defining which technology is appropriate to cope with all the challenges – e.g. (IoT infrastructure which uses LoRaWan connectivity. We bought the needed equipment and agreed to test it at Doppler Winery. If the defined solution delivers good results, it will be good news for many farmers in the LL and around the country who are facing similar problems.

On 19.05.2023 and 16.06.2023 we set up sensor infrastructure at the demo farm (Doppler Winery).

On 15.11.2023 we organised the first annual LL meeting at the demo farm Doppler Winery. As part of the WP3, we delivered a workshop with the aim of identification of the resources, capabilities, collaborations and innovations

present and needed to solve the LL FAS problem statement; Another task of the same workshop was to analyse the digital ecosystem conduciveness by using the Socio-ecological framework to explore how it supports/hinders the resources, capabilities, collaborations and innovations necessary to address the LL FAS problem statement. Second activity of the annual LL meeting was focus group (WP4). The goal was to explore participant's views on the social, environmental, and economic costs and benefits associated with digitalization in agriculture.

With this project, we want to extend the activities of our LL. In addition to monitoring the impact of digital solutions on viticulture, we also want to support beekeepers and bee care. Therefore, we defined our second pilot (or FAS) related to beekeeping.

We discussed the problem and a possible (technology-based) solution with beekeeper Marko Cesar. The beekeeper has bee colonies in 3 locations (one at home, one is moved around the Pohorje hills, the third is in Prekmurje (more than 50 Km away). Challenges he presented:

1. Climate change is changing the situation of life of bees enormously. There is not enough pasture for bees in the valley. Meadows are mowed too soon, too much heat and drought, and too much rain are not good for bees. He moves the bees on better (but distant) locations.

It is important he knows the micro-climate of the (distant) beehives because this is how he monitors health and nutrition of bees. If he would have data about micro-climate, he could better plan his visits (whether he has to feed them when it rains, make a brood box on hot days, collect honey when it is full etc.).

2. Distance between beehives also means driving a sample of honey to be tested for more than 50 Km away. This is mandatory if he wants to label the right type of honey and sell it as a certain (more valuable) type.

Researchers at UL helped with defining which IoT solution is appropriate to cope with the challenges – e.g. (IoT scales, that use GPS signal only the moment the data is sent via SMS). We bought the needed equipment and agreed to test it at Beekeeping Cesar. If the defined solution delivers good results it will contribute to the expansion of beekeeping, the preservation of bees, and pollination, which is important for all other crops. Despite the migration of bees to more favourable and healthier locations, the technology helps us to save time and cost of transportation and thus less CO2 emissions.

In April 2024 we interviewed the two participating farmers about Social-Human centred costs and benefits.

In May 2024 our first virtual demo farm event took place. We presented lessons learned at Doppler winery in the first year of using chosen IoT+LoRaWan technology.

2. Focal action situation and state of digitalisation

Starting from the focal action situation, identify the process transformed by digital technology to be considered for process modelling and the state of digitalisation of your living lab.

Given the problem statements - Doppler Winery:

How to use digital technology in viticulture, in order to affect the environmental, economic, and social aspects of sustainability to find best/better IoT infrastructure for winemakers that would solve current problems with connectivity and very rugged territory with different microclimate in same vineyard.

The digital solution:

The digital solution is a vineyard monitoring system, which consists of sensor infrastructure to measure different weather and viticultural parameters, for communication we are using LoRaWAN network and data platform to manage data aggregation. The mobile monitoring application that UL will develop will give the farmers data about climate situation in their vineyards, and information if any values are exceeding limit values. The application will act as a decision support system for the farmers.

Given the problem statements - Beekeeping Cesar:

How to use digital technology in beekeeping, in order to affect the environmental, economic, and social aspects: to preserve the bees, ensure pollination, ensure better yield of honey, and save transport related expenses (money, time, CO2 emissions).

The digital solution:

The digital solution is IoT scales that are placed under a beehive, use GPS signal only the moment the data is sent via SMS. The beekeeper can set the time the scale measures the climate data or call the scale and get the current data immediately.

2.1. Shortly present the focal action situation of your Living Lab and any other information you deem relevant to describe the specific context

Expand on the focal action situation with contextual information on your living lab.

The Living Lab Smart Villages Network is located in three different regions in Slovenia, connecting the east and west of the country. Our Living Lab connects farmers, researchers, technology providers, and government representatives. Together, we have fostered a 'learning culture,' collaborating on various projects over the years. Traditionally our primary focus was harnessing IoT technology in wine production, but with Codecs we want to expand our field of work to beekeeping and honey production.

We have been monitoring, developing and testing IoT solutions for the purpose of use in viticulture for many years. In relation: sensor infrastructure, communication technology, data collection and processing, user interface/monitoring, there were always problems due to rough terrain or poor communication coverage. Technology is advancing very quickly, now it seems that we finally have a workable solution to the aforementioned geographical and communication challenges and is also appropriate to test it in another domain (beekeeping).

The LL is focused on using digital technology in viticulture and beekeeping, in order to affect the environmental, economic, and social aspects of sustainability, with the following objectives: 1) Environmental (reducing use of water and pesticides in the winegrowing process; lowering CO2 emissions, less treatments in the vineyards, preserving

the bees and ensuring better pollination 2) Social impact (sustainable business management, time management; 3) Economic (improved farm profitability).

The LL has introduced a IoT infrastructure which uses dispersed sensors (measures soil moisture, rain and leaf wetness) and communicates (transmits data) on LoRaWAN network for winemakers. We will upgrade the system with a new mobile application, which is in the process of development.

In the field of beekeeping, we started testing IoT supported remote control of beehives, which is an increasingly expected scenario for many other beekeepers due to the changed environmental conditions.

2.2. Make explicit the problem statement

Within the description provided above, identify a problem statement. You can simply extract the sentences from the previous text or elaborate it with further details.

Winemakers in Slovenia face difficulties related to the connectivity and very rugged territory with different microclimate in same vineyard. This affects the farm's profitability, but also influences the environmental and social aspects. The winemakers need a dispersed network of sensors (not one weather station) and a stable "machine to machine" communication in order to understand the situation in vineyards and make an informed decision. This is particularly important for organic farms.

Beekeepers have trouble maintaining healthy bee colonies. They are plagued by problems due to climate change, which forces them to move their apiaries to remote locations. Therefore, they need systems for remote control of the situation in remote beehives.

2.3. Explain why your living lab identifies with *Digitalised*

Based on the project activity carried out during the general assembly in December 2023, you have identified your living lab with case 3: **Digitalised – Digital solution adopted, to be evaluated**. This is a state in which, after a first period of in-field testing, the digital solution has been adopted within the LL. The LL is able to evaluate the technology and provide comparison with the process before the introduction of the digital solution.

In case you think that another case is more relevant for your living lab (Case 1. *Zero Digital – No digital solution in place, digital solution not identified* or Case 2. *Digitalising – Digital solution identified, not yet fully adopted*), you can switch to a different procedure for data collection and refer to the corresponding template. Please, inform the task leaders of your decision.

Having in mind the problem statement formulated in the previous question, briefly explain your choice.

Given the problem statement – Doppler Winery:

"How to use digital technology in viticulture, in order to affect the environmental, economic, and social aspects of sustainability to find best IoT infrastructure for winemakers that would solve current problems with connectivity and very rugged territory with different microclimate in same vineyard."

The LL has introduced a solution, a vineyard monitoring system that consists of sensor infrastructure to measure different weather and viticultural parameters, sending them over the LoRaWAN network to a data platform to manage data aggregation (ThingsBoard). The network of sensors was implemented at Doppler Winery at the beginning of the project and, now we are able to evaluate the technology and provide comparison with the process before the introduction of the digital solution.

Given the problem statements - Beekeeping Cesar:

“How to use digital technology in beekeeping, in order to affect the environmental, economic, and social aspects: to preserve the bees, ensure pollination, ensure better yield of honey, and save transport related expenses (money, time, CO2 emissions).”

The LL has introduced IoT scales that are placed under beehives on 3 remote locations. We can evaluate the technology and provide comparison.

3. Digital solution

Present the digital solution that you have adopted and explain the motivation behind it.

Doppler Winery:

We adopted a solution that uses a network of sensors, that are dispersed around the farmers land (not one weather station that is commonly used). The process of measurement of viticultural parameters includes the collection of data for the following parameters: soil moisture, leaf wetness, and rainfall. Sensors use standard AAA batteries, and the devices can work up to 10 years before battery replacement is needed. Sensors have a long range, on average of 15km, and they communicate with the Gateway located on top of the hill. For machine-to-machine communication they use LoRaWan (Low-power wide-area network) technology.

The collected data is sent to the LoRaWAN server for further analysis. Sensor infrastructure works via LoRaWAN This type of connectivity has been chosen due to the low energy consumption, long-range, and easy configuration. This set up needs no further costs and we can privately set up the whole network through a private LoRa server. The communication architecture between the sensor system and the server is the following: devices send data to LoRaWAN gateway and then, the gateway sends the data to the server and platform. Gateway needs to be connected to Ethernet or Wi-Fi network.

The data collection model is implemented on the Thingsboard platform, where sensor platform data are stored and are available for further use via an application programming interface (API). Thingsboard is an open-source platform used for device management, data collection, visualization and processing. Thingsboard provides MQTT-, HTTP-, CoAP- and LwM2M-based APIs and enables a server-side infrastructure for IoT applications. The data pushed from devices can be visualized in real-time in an end-user dashboard. With rule nodes in a rule engine and processed data, an alarm can be created to support the vine producers’ processes.

For the future, the data reported by the sensors will be the basis for the development of new predictive models that will enhance the mobile vineyard monitoring application.

The main purposes of introducing this technology are:

- 1) Control and reduction of the use of water and substances in the winegrowing process
- 2) Lowering CO2 emissions (less treatments in the vineyards)
- 3) Saving time
- 4) Improved farm profitability

Beekeeping Cesar:

IoT Scales measure weather parameters: rain, wind, nest temperature, external temperature, relative humidity

Battery duration up to 10 years.

Every scale has a SIM card because it uses GSM/GPRS in order to send daily SMS to the mobile phone. Signal is needed only for sending SMS.

The main purposes of introducing this technology are:

- 1) Better control over the beekeeping process and keeping bees healthy and alive
- 2) Lowering CO2 emissions (driving to the beehives and to the testing of type of honey)
- 3) Saving time
- 4) Improved farm profitability (Economic Benefits: Beekeeping provides honey, beeswax, and economic opportunities for beekeepers.)
- 5) Environmental:
 - Pollination: Bees pollinate crops, ensuring food production and biodiversity
 - Ecosystem Stability: They maintain plant diversity, supporting wildlife habitats

3.1. Which digital solution did the living lab introduce?

Briefly describe the digital solution identified by the Living Lab. Indicate the level of maturity of the digital solution in the context of the LL by choosing among 1. proof of concept; 2. prototype; 3. pilot; 4. novel system; 5. mature system and provide additional relevant information.

Doppler Winery:

The digital solution introduced is a vineyard monitoring system, which employs IoT + LoRaWAN technology for a resilient infrastructure addressing connectivity issues, rugged terrain, and diverse microclimates in the same vineyard.

[Maturity]

We identify the solution to be a 4. novel system. It connects various already known and stable building blocks (data storage, communication technology, sensor infrastructure) in a new way that works in the specific environment.

Beekeeping Cesar:

The digital solution introduced is a IoT supported scale that is placed under beehives, it sends relevant daily data to the beekeeper and helps them with decision making.

[Maturity]

We identify the solution to be a 4. novel system. The system itself that has been on the market for some time, but it is expensive and not common to be used by (small) beekeepers that are very important for contributing to environmental health.

3.2. Explain why and how the living lab has introduced this digital solution.

Provide a motivation for having chosen the solution considering its suitability, feasibility and acceptability. Explain how the digital solution was identified.

The LL Smart Villages Network, connects farmers, researchers, tech providers, and government representatives. Together, we have fostered a 'learning culture,' collaborating on various projects over the years. Challenges in rural lives were documented using SEROI+ methodology, where we defined goals, performed stakeholder mapping, co-designed possible solutions and implemented/tested several of them.

With Codecs we were given the opportunity to test a new solution that had been maturing for several years, but the technology was not yet at this level.

The main purpose of introducing this solution (IoT dispersed sensor infrastructure + LoRaWAN) is the ability to influence the environmental, economic and social aspect of sustainability in agriculture, by having control of the water and substance use in the winegrowing process, influencing the CO2 emissions (with less treatments in the vineyards), achieving time efficiency and improved farm profitability.

The goal is to test a new IoT infrastructure and connectivity technology in vineyards, measuring microclimate on several parts of vineyards, to help the farmer make an informed decision, if a treatment is needed or not (spraying etc.) and where exactly. The main goal is to reduce the number of treatments in the vineyard due to IoT support and more data available.

Beekeeping is important for success in viticulture, so we are testing the impact of IoT technology in this area as well.

4. Process after digital solution

Describe **how the current process works**.

4.1. Who are the actors involved now?

Identify all actors involved in the current process. For each actor specify its role, the number of people in that role involved in the LL and other relevant information.

- Farmers (the wine producers, beekeeper)
- University of Ljubljana (UL), a group of researchers from the ICT department at Faculty of electrical engineering with profiles: Project manager, Data scientists, IoT expert, Mobile app designer, LL Coordinator
- Technology providers (for IoT equipment)
- Business consultant
- Policy makers (Member of Ministry for Digital transformation monitors activities)

4.2. What are the resources involved in the process?

Identify all resources involved in the process.

Resources may refer to: physical assets (land, tractors, crops, animals, etc.); financing (funds); technologies (hardware and software solutions); knowledge (scientific reports, training, etc.).

Provide a comprehensive description of the digital technologies and components involved.

Physical resources

- Land
- Water (own water source)
- Machinery

Technological resources

- IoT sensors
- LoRaWAN technology
- digital control of the wine cellar (digital barrels, airflow and ventilation, digital door)

Knowledge resources

- Agronomy
- Tourism
- Heritage - knowledge passed down from generation to generation
- Digital skills
- Data management

Motivation

- Family (family-run business)
- Conversion to organic farming (new markets, higher price)

4.3. What are the activities carried out by actors using the available resources?

Starting from each actor listed in 4.1, identify all activities in the process carried out by the actor and provide a numbered sequence of activities.

In case more than one actor (e.g., farmer) is involved in the process and they perform DIFFERENT tasks, repeat each actor grouping their activities. You can also use different names according to their specialised role. For instance: farmer 1-2-3 –feeding, farmer 4-5 – milking, ...

Instead, if more actors are involved but they perform the SAME tasks, you do not need to repeat the activities for each actor.

You can also add further information (for example a **SPECIFIC CONDITION** or **FREQUENCY of ACTIVITY**), but the **ACTOR, ACTION** and **MOTIVATION** shall be present.

Farmer (Beekeeper Cesar):

On a daily basis, the beekeeper receives a notification via SMS because he/she wants to know the environment status of the bees in the remote location.

In case of significant weather change/ not good weather situation the beekeeper drives to the beehive location because needs to feed the bees, bring them water etc.

In case he receives data indicating that honey is to be harvested, the beekeeper drives to the beehive location to collect the honey.

If interested, the beekeeper can request the current data in the beehives because he wants to keep track of bees' wellbeing and plan future activities.

Farmer (Dopler Winery):

On a daily basis, the winemaker checks data from the data dashboard to plan her activity in the vineyard because she wants to perform treatments (organic spraying) in the vineyard only if and where necessary;

In case of rain, the winemaker checks the rain level in the last 24 hours and in the last 60 minutes because she will need to plan a treatment (organic spraying) asap after rains stops;

If interested, the winemaker can access the dashboard to see all data collected because she wants to keep track of every part of vineyard and plan future activities;

Performed treatments, planned activities and data accessed by the winemaker

The total surface area of viticulture production on the farm is 8ha. Out of these 8ha, IoT sensors collect data from 6.5ha, and the rest 1.5ha do not contribute to this data collection. The production yield is 3-4 T/ha annually. The aim in this case is to protect the products from fungicides with the right use of chemicals designed to protect crops from diseases that can negatively affect their growth and production. This is done by spraying treatments in the vineyards. For this, the winemaker uses two types of phytosanitary products, copper and sulphur. The spraying is usually done with a 90 HP Tractor, Carraro TRX9800, and the fuel used is Diesel, with an approximate consumption of 7L/h or 70 kWh/h. The spreading equipment used is a sprayer of 400L capacity. Rarely they do it manually in cases of too much rain on steep terrain, where it is not safe to use a tractor.

Frequency of the on-field activities

More precisely on this activity by different scenarios, reference scenario (non-digitalised) and digitalised:

Non digitalised: The spraying of plant protection products each year, is about 34h/ha per year that means 2 hours/week/hectare*17 weeks=34 hours/year/hectare. Spraying season lasts from May until middle of August for approx. 4 months =17 weeks, meaning 16 hours/week*17 weeks =272 hours/year. The time of spraying takes 2h/ha (16h/8ha per week).

In this scenario, 2kg/ha is used from the product copper (commercial name Curzate), and 3kg/ha is used from the product Pepelin (sulphur). That applies in total for 17 treatments in a year. Water used is 300L/ha or that equals to 40,800 liters, Copper: 272kg, Sulphur: 408kg. The work was done once a week from May until middle of August.

Digitalized: The spraying of plant protection products each year, is estimated that it last for about 28h/ha per year, which means 2-3 treatments less spraying per season, in comparison with the non-digitalised scenario. This was difficult to measure more precisely because of the terrible weather last two seasons, but approximately 2 hours/week/hectare*14 weeks=28 hours/year/hectare.

In this scenario same number of products applies as well, 2kg/ha is used from the product copper (commercial name Curzate), and 3kg/ha is used from the product Pepelin (sulphur). That applies to a total of four treatments in a year. Water used is 300L/ha or that equals 33,600 liters, Copper: 224kg, Sulphur: 336kg. The work was done once a week/10 days from May until middle of August.

Conclusion:

Non-Digitalized Scenario:

In the non-digitalized scenario, the frequency of spraying happens weekly for 17 weeks (May to mid-August), in total of 17 spraying treatments, which required 34 hours per hectare annually, with 272 hours total for an 8-hectare field. The application of copper (272 kg) and sulphur (408 kg) consumed 40,800 liters of water per year.

Digitalized Scenario:

In the digitalized approach, the frequency of spraying happened weekly or every 10 days for 14 weeks (May to mid-August), in a total of 14 spraying treatments, which reduced spraying to 28 hours per hectare annually, saving 2–3 treatments per season compared to the non-digitalized scenario. There is also a reduction in resource use, in

both copper (224 kg) and sulphur (336 kg), with total water consumption reduced to 33,600 liters annually, reflecting improved efficiency and sustainability.

The above information can be summaries in the following table:

Aspect	Non-Digitalized Scenario	Digitalized Scenario
Spraying Frequency	Weekly for 17 weeks (May to mid-August)	Weekly or every 10 days for 14 weeks (May to mid-August)
Total Spraying Time	34 hours/hectare/year	28 hours/hectare/year
Spraying Time (8 ha)	272 hours/year (16 hours/week * 17 weeks)	224 hours/year (16 hours/week * 14 weeks)
Treatments per Year	17 treatments	14 treatments
Copper Usage (Curzate)	272 kg/year (2 kg/ha * 17 treatments)	224 kg/year (2 kg/ha * 14 treatments)
Sulphur Usage (Pepelin)	408 kg/year (3 kg/ha * 17 treatments)	336 kg/year (3 kg/ha * 14 treatments)
Water Usage	40,800 liters/year (300 liters/ha * 17 treatments)	33,600 liters/year (300 liters/ha * 14 treatments)
Reduction (Digitalized)	—	2-3 fewer treatments, 6 hours/hectare less, saving 48 kg Copper, 72 kg Sulphur, and 7,200 liters of water

Table 1: On field activities at the Doppler Winery

Technology provider:

Technology provider troubleshoots or assists with the data interpretation because they want their system to work and have satisfied customers, that will lead to new customers;

University of Ljubljana:

Researchers from the University of Ljubljana exchange communication with LL members because they want to support this collaboration, want to maintain a conducive environment for testing and developing new innovative solutions in the future.

Researchers from the University of Ljubljana access the dashboard to see aggregated stats at Doppler winery in case they ask for assistance and because the UL wants to develop mobile app in order to better support the winemaker.

Business consultant:

Monitors the project and locally supports the farmers with decision making)

Policy makers:

Member of Ministry for Digital transformation monitors activities on the project and contributes when policy related information is relevant/needed. Wants to collaborate to stay connected to “real life” innovative practices.

4.4. What are the advantages of the current process for each actor?

Identify the advantages of the current process for each actor involved in terms of economic increase, resources optimisation, and advantages in process management

The main advantages are the following:

- The monitoring system serves the farmers by providing data of the parameters which allows them to take appropriate actions if and where needed.
- The LL and UL benefit from strong and collaborative network of stakeholders that share knowledge and best practices. This ensures the network is agile when new projects arise.
- Technology providers benefit when their product is used by wider audiences.
- Policy makers benefit by getting insights from the lessons learned in piloting activities in communities.

5. Process *before* digital solution

Recall the process in the past and describe **how the system worked before** the introduction of the digital solution.

Both farmers had to rely on data from national weather stations and plan activities from that.

That data is not accurate, so the activities (treatments of the vineyard / visit to the remote beehives) were sometimes performed “just in case”. In other scenario, if they missed the “window” to perform the activity, that could result in yield loss or death of bee colonies.

5.1. Has the introduction of the digital solution required the involvement of new actors? If yes, which ones?

Start from the list of actors provided in 4.1 and identify the actors that have been involved by the introduction of the digital solution.

New actors are:

- Technology provider (sensors + LoraWAN)
- IoT/M2M expert (for architecture design)

Technology provider troubleshoots or assists with the data interpretation because they want their system to work and have satisfied customers, that will lead to new customers;

The IoT/M2M expert played a vital role in ensuring the success of the implementation by providing technical expertise, designing a reliable and secure system, and ensuring the proper functioning of the IoT sensors and network. More precisely, the activities were related to:

1. System Architecture Design: Develop the overall architecture for the IoT system, considering the sensors, connectivity, data storage, and processing infrastructure. This includes choosing the right technologies, platforms,

and protocols (LoRaWAN). Ensure the system is scalable and can integrate with other technologies or platforms as needed. Implement necessary security measures to protect the IoT ecosystem from potential breaches, ensuring data security and privacy.

2. Selection of Sensors and Equipment: Recommend sensor types, suggest the best sensors for monitoring vineyard conditions based on the project's requirements. Ensure the selected sensors are compatible with the communication protocols and platform being used.

3. Connectivity and Network Design: Design the communication network (LoRaWAN), assess the vineyard's terrain and environment to ensure optimal placement of devices for reliable signal coverage. Define and optimize the data transmission protocols, ensuring low latency and minimal data loss.

4. Implementation Support: Provide support with the installation of sensors, gateways, and other hardware, ensuring proper placement for accurate data collection.

5. Monitoring and Maintenance: Propose monitoring tools for real-time data analysis, ensuring that data collected from the sensors is accurate and actionable.

6. Data Management and Analysis: Define how data will flow from sensors to cloud or edge computing systems for analysis, ensuring efficient data processing and storage.

7. Compliance and Documentation: Ensure that the IoT architecture complies with local regulations and standards related to wireless communication, data privacy, and environmental considerations.

8. Training and Knowledge Transfer: Offer training sessions for the project team or vineyard staff to ensure they can manage and troubleshoot the system independently. Ensure a smooth handover of the system once the design and installation are complete, providing necessary support during the transition.

5.2. Have actors been removed because of the introduction of the digital solution? If yes, which ones?

List any actors that were removed from the process *after* the introduction of digital solution. If possible, connect the removed actors to the actors added in replacement (list in question 4.1).

The solution removed the following actor:

- National /Austrian Weather agency (open access)

5.3. Which new resources have been added?

Start from the list in 4.2 and identify the resources that have been added after the introduction of the digital solution. Based on resources classification in 4.2, provide the list of added resources.

Provide a comprehensive description of the digital technologies and components involved.

Technological resources:

- IoT sensors
- LoRaWAN Gateway
- IoT beehive scale
- Refractometer and conductometer

Refractometer in Beekeeping:

Purpose: A refractometer is used to measure the water content in honey. This is crucial because honey with too much moisture can ferment and spoil, while honey with the proper moisture level (generally 17-18%) will remain stable for long-term storage.

How it works: Beekeepers place a small sample of honey on the refractometer's prism, and by looking through the lens, they can see the percentage of water content based on how light is refracted through the honey.

Why it's important: Monitoring water content ensures honey is harvested at the right time, which is important for maintaining high quality and preventing fermentation.

Conductometer in Beekeeping:

Purpose: A conductometer measures the electrical conductivity of honey. This property is used to differentiate between different types of honey, particularly floral honey (from nectar) and honeydew honey (from tree sap).

How it works: Conductivity is determined by the presence of minerals and salts in honey. Honeydew honey has higher conductivity than floral honey because it contains more minerals.

Why it's important: Beekeepers and honey producers use conductometers to classify the honey type (honeydew vs. floral), which can influence honey pricing and quality assessment. It's also used to ensure the honey meets certain regulatory or market standards, especially in Europe.

Conclusion: Previously, the beekeeper faced significant logistical challenges, as their three apiary locations across Slovenia were remote and difficult to access. Sampling required traveling to the sites, collecting honey, and returning to a city for samplings analysis. With the introduction of refractometers and conductometers at these locations, analyses can now be performed directly on-site, eliminating unnecessary travel and significantly improving efficiency and time management.

5.4. Which resources have been removed?

Based on the list in 4.2, list any resources that have been removed.

Additional explanations for the updated version of this report:

National weather agency and Austrian weather Agency - it is replaced with own data.

5.5. Before the introduction of the digital solution, how were the activities carried out by actors?

Follow this procedure:

1. Copy-paste all the content that you wrote in answer 4.3
2. Remove the actors that were not part of the process when the digital solution was not introduced and respective actions (list in 5.1)
3. Remove any other action that was not part of the process when the digital solution was not introduced yet
4. Add actors that belonged to the previous process (list in 5.2), and a numbered sequence of respective actions
5. Add any other actions that were part of the process when the digital solution was not introduced yet

Follow the structure proposed in 4.3 to describe the activities.

Farmer (Beekeeper Cesar):

On a daily basis, the beekeeper checked the National weather agency and Austrian weather Agency data because he/she wants to know the environment status of the bees in remote location;
In case he intuitively predicted significant weather change/ not good weather situation the beekeeper drives to the beehive location because needs to see in person, if he needs to feed the bees, bring them water, collect the honey, etc.

Farmer (Doppler Winery):

On a daily basis, the winemaker checked the National weather agency and Austrian weather Agency data because he/she wants to know the environment status of the vineyards;
In case he intuitively predicted significant weather change/ not good weather situation the winemaker drives to the vineyard because needs to see in person, if he needs to irrigate (in case of dryness), spray pesticides (to prevent diseases), etc.

6. Transition

6.1. How did the living lab deal with the transition to the new system?

Reflect on the **transition phase that was necessary for the adoption of the digital solution** in the LL and provide a list of the progressive steps that you took for the setup of the system.

The transition included approximately these consecutive steps:

1. Assessment of the current situation, needs and problems
2. Purchase of all necessary hardware for the farms adopting new digital solution
3. Physical Installation of the equipment and set up
4. Test
5. Co-design and development of mobile app
6. Interventions when significant weather forecast (e.g. frost in April)

7. General feedback and conclusion

7.1. Feedback from coordinators

Please provide feedback about your experience as a coordinator answering the following questions:

1. Were you able to collect sufficient information? -Yes
2. Were the templates and guidelines helpful? -Yes
3. Did you encounter problems in filling the template? -No
4. What were the main challenges in following the proposed procedure? - Obtaining data from different sources.
5. What were the most challenging questions? -5.5
6. Would you suggest any changes to the procedure? Why?

Please report anything relevant about the overall experience.

7.2. Feedback from participants

Please consider the viewpoints of the participants and provide feedback about the experience, answering the following questions:

1. Did the participants encounter difficulties in answering your questions?

Beekeeper: No

Winemaker: No

2. What were the most challenging questions?

- We didn't experience challenges with any particular questions.

3. Were they engaged in the conversation?

Beekeeper: Yes

Winemaker: Yes

4. Did they feel involved in the process?

Beekeeper: Yes

Winemaker: Yes

5. Were they willing to share information?

Beekeeper: Yes

Winemaker: Yes

Please report anything relevant about the overall experience.

7.3. Short survey

		Strongly disagree	Disagree	Undecided	Agree	Strongly agree
1	It was easy to come out with answers.				x	
2	I think I will reuse the procedure in the future when dealing with the analysis of process transformation.			x		
3	I made a lot of effort to think about actors, resources and activities.					x
4	I would recommend the use of this procedure.		x			

5	The procedure helped us to better realise the impact of the digital transformation.					X
6	I found the question on the transition useful to reflect on the steps taken.				X	
7	It was challenging to recall the process before digital solution.		X			
8	The procedure followed did not help to describe the process transformation.		X			
9	I would apply a different procedure if I had to repeat a similar activity.				X	
10	I had to highly adapt the questions when collecting data directly from stakeholders.		X			

8. Additional material and transcripts

Please report here any additional material that was produced along the experience, including mock-ups and software snapshots. The additional material can include pictures of the workshops and focus groups, posters and snapshots of the boards used in the meetings. You may also upload the additional material in the dedicated folder on Teams. Please briefly describe here the content of the additional material so that the reader can make sense of what is it.

In case transcripts of the data collection activities are available, provide a list indicating the type of activities (interviews, focus groups, workshops), date and reference to the corresponding file. Upload the anonymised transcripts in the dedicated folder on Teams.

The following additional material will be uploaded to the dedicated folder:

1. **Workshop** on identification of the resources, capabilities, collaborations and innovations and analysis of the digital ecosystem conduciveness by using the Socio-ecological framework (WP3, 15.11.2024).
 2. **Focus group** on participant’s views on the social, environmental, and economic costs and benefits associated with digitalization in agriculture (WP4, 15.11.2024).
- **Two Interviews** on social -Human centred C&B analysis (WP4, 12.04.2024 and 25.04.2024).
 - Additional data collection from the winemaker through **phone interview** (October 2024).